

BIODT
biodiversitydigitaltwin

How can cross-use digital modelling tools help in nature protection?

Report of webinar March 2025

Introduction:

Strengthening Digital Twin Synergies

The BioDT project continues to advance biodiversity digital twins, bringing together researchers, policymakers, and technology experts to explore the future of digital modelling tools. On 27 February 2025, BioDT hosted a webinar focused on cross-project collaboration in the digital twin landscape, featuring contributions from major European initiatives, including Destination Earth (DestinE), ClimateDT, TerraDT, DT-GEO, and InterTwin.

The webinar attracted over 90 participants from 24 countries, including representatives from research institutions, governmental agencies, and technology providers.

Key Discussions and Takeaways

Digital Twins for Climate Adaptation and Environmental Modelling

Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT Services) opened the webinar by discussing the latest climate change trends and their impact on biodiversity. Following her introduction, experts in the **digital twin field** presented the main objectives of their respective initiatives:

- **Thomas Geenen (ECMWF, Destination Earth - DestinE)** highlighted the **European Commission's strategy for digital twins** and the importance of collaboration across EU-funded projects. He explained how initiatives like **DestinE** play a crucial role in enhancing environmental decision-making through advanced modelling tools.
- **Jenni Kontkanen (CSC – IT Center for Science)** introduced **DestinE's Climate Change Adaptation Digital Twin**, explaining how it generates **high-resolution climate projections** to support **policy development and adaptation strategies** for climate resilience. She also presented the newly funded **TerraDT project**, which extends DestinE's infrastructure by integrating **new modelling components** to simulate the effects of **glaciers, sea ice, and aerosols** on climate.
- **Gabriela Zuquim (CSC – IT Center for Science)** showcased **BioDT's prototype digital twins (pDTs)** and their role in **predicting biodiversity changes** under different climate scenarios. She described how **BioDT leverages high-performance computing and cloud services** to model **species dynamics, habitat loss, and policy interventions**.
- **Andrea Manzi (EGI Foundation)** introduced **interTwin**, a **digital twin engine for science** that co-designs and implements an **interdisciplinary Digital Twin Engine** by developing an **open-science platform**.

 Ramon Carbonell (Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas - CSIC) presented **DT-GEO**, a **digital twin for geophysical extremes**. He explained how **DT-GEO applies digital twin technology and exascale computing** to develop **cutting-edge tools for modelling Earth's most dynamic systems**, helping **communities and decision-makers** make informed and proactive decisions.

Panel Discussions:

Opportunities, limitations and future opportunities

Following the introduction, two panel discussions brought together experts from **BioDT, DestinE, DT-GEO, and InterTwin** to explore the **challenges and opportunities** in digital twin development. The key insights from the discussions are summarised below:

 Interoperability remains a major challenge: Digital twins must align on **architectural frameworks, data standards, and integration methodologies** to enable cross-use and seamless collaboration.

 AI and machine learning are increasingly enhancing digital twin simulations: DestinE is making significant investments in **AI-driven Earth System Models** to improve the **accuracy and efficiency** of environmental modelling.

 Long-term sustainability is critical: The continued viability of digital twins depends on their integration into **European research infrastructures** such as **EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)** and **EuroHPC supercomputing networks**.

Interactive Session: **Audience Insights**

Participants engaged in live polling to share their perspectives on digital twin applications. Key findings included:

- **The most effective ways to mitigate environmental risks** include **predictive modelling, standardised data sharing, and cross-sector collaboration.**
- **Challenges in digital twin adoption** include **technical complexity, lack of harmonised data, and limited accessibility to non-experts.**
- **User-friendly interfaces and educational initiatives** were identified as essential for increasing the adoption of digital twins across different sectors.

Next Steps and Future Collaboration

The webinar concluded with **Anja Radonjić (Trust-IT Services)** summarising the key discussion points and outlining opportunities for future collaboration. The next steps for each initiative are as follows:

- **DestinE:** Advancing towards a more operational state by integrating **AI and machine learning** to enhance interactivity and improve the user interface.
- **ClimateDT:** Conducting **first operational simulations** and further developing the system.
- **TerraDT:** Establishing the groundwork for future developments.
- **DT-GEO:** Addressing **long-term sustainability** and exploring how digital twins can be maintained on a European scale.
- **InterTwin:** Preparing for the **final release of software and digital twin demonstrators**, as well as the **project's final event**.
- **BioDT:** **Finalising prototype digital twins (pDTs)**, preparing for their official launch, and focusing on **sustainability and long-term usability**.

Did you miss the webinar?

The full webinar recording is available on the BioDT YouTube channel.

in collaboration with

 DT-GEO

WEBINAR February 27, 2025 15:00-16:00 CET

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